

REFERENCES

Reviewed Sources

- Ajayi, O.O., Bagula, A.B. and Maluleke, H.C. 2020. Africa 3: A continental network model to enable the African Fourth Industrial Revolution. *IEEE Access*, 8: 196847–196864.
- Alabi, A.O. and Mutula, S.M. 2022. Human development for the fourth industrial revolution: Which way for Sub-Saharan Africa? *Development Southern Africa*, 39(4): 528–542.
- Alabi, M.O., Telukdarie, A. and van Rensburg, N.J. 2019. Industry 4.0 and water industry: A South African perspective and readiness. *Proceedings of the American Society for Engineering Management 2019 International Annual Conference*, 1–12.
- Al-Maskari, A., Al Riyami, T. and Ghnimi, S. 2024. Factors affecting students' preparedness for the fourth industrial revolution in higher education institutions. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 16(1): 246–264.
- Borrageiro, K. and Mennega, N. 2023. Essential skills needed in the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR): A systematic literature review. *2023 IST-Africa Conference (IST-Africa)*, 1–13.
- Carrim, N. 2022. 4IR in South Africa and some of its educational implications. *Journal of Education*, 86: 1–18.*
- Chauke, T.A., Mkhize, T.R., Methi, L. and Dlamini, N. 2024. Postgraduate students' perceptions on the benefits associated with artificial intelligence tools on academic success: In case of ChatGPT AI tool. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, 6(1): 44–59.*
- Chilunjika, A., Intauno, K. and Chilunjika, S.R. 2022. Artificial intelligence and public sector human resource management in South Africa: Opportunities, challenges and prospects. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20.
- Dlamini, P., Chizema, T. and Van Greunen, D. 2023a. SMS connectivity and information display in 4IR projects for small-scale farmers. *2023 IST-Africa Conference (IST-Africa)*, 1–8.
- Dlamini, Z. and Kheswa, E. 2023. The progress of implementation of 4IR technologies in KwaZulu-Natal. *2023 IST-Africa Conference (IST-Africa)*, 1–11.
- Donald, M.F., Bophelo, H. and Rivalani, M.H. 2023. The use of technology in higher education: Implications of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. In Makua, M. et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 10th Focus Conference (TFC 2023)*, Vol. 788: 426–436. Atlantis Press SARL.*
- Ebekozien, A., Aigbavboa, C.O., Aliu, J. and Thwala, W.D. 2024. Generic skills of future built environment practitioners in South Africa: Unexplored mechanism via students' perception. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 22(2): 561–577.
- Fataar, A. 2020. The emergence of an education policy dispositif in South Africa: An analysis of educational discourses associated with the fourth industrial revolution. *Journal of Education (University of KwaZulu-Natal)*, 80: 5–24.*
- Harmse, A. and Wadee, A.A. 2019. Decolonising ICT curricula in the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *2019 International Multidisciplinary Information Technology and Engineering Conference (IMITEC)*, 1–10.

- Hlobo, M., Moloi, T. and Mhlanga, D. 2021. The Fourth Industrial Revolution in South Africa's private higher education institutions and further education and training colleges. *IICE-2021 and i-Society 2021*, 37–48.*
- John, A., Clinton, A. and Thwala, W.D. 2021. Driving the Fourth Industrial Revolution initiative through university and industry collaborations. *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 26(2): 211–230.
- Kademete, E. and Twinomurinzi, H. 2019. The ineffectiveness of technology adoption models in the 4IR era: A case of SMEs in South Africa. *2019 Open Innovations (OI)*, 252–261.
- Karjalainen, J., Heinonen, S. and Shaw, M. 2019. Peer-to-peer and circular economy principles in the fourth industrial revolution: New risks and opportunities. *2019 International Conference on the Domestic Use of Energy (DUE)*, 220–230.
- Kayembe, C. 2019. Challenges and opportunities for education in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *African Journal of Public Affairs*, 11(3): 79–94.
- Kishore, N., Pretorius, J. and Chattopadhyay, G. 2022. Learning, un-learning, and relearning in 4IR in rural environments. *2022 International Conference on Maintenance and Intelligent Asset Management (ICMIAM)*, 1–6.*
- Landsberg, E. and van den Berg, L. 2023. 4IR skills in the current South African accountancy curricula: A systematic literature review. *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 37(3): 177–201.*
- Lubinga, S., Maramura, T.C. and Masiya, T. 2023. The Fourth Industrial Revolution adoption: Challenges in South African higher education institutions. *Journal of Culture and Values in Education*, 6(2): 1–17.*
- Lukas, L.S. and van der Poll, J.A. 2022. A conceptual framework for business model innovation of South African smart aerotropoli. In Arai, K. (Ed.), *Advances in Information and Communication*, Vol. 439: 33–52. Springer International Publishing.
- Mabe, K. and Bwalya, K.J. 2022. Critical soft skills for information and knowledge management practitioners in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *SA Journal of Information Management*, 24(1): a1519.
- Mabungela, M. 2023. Artificial Intelligence and automation in the world of work: A threat to employees? *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 8(4): 135–146.
- Madumo, O.S. and Kimaro, J.R. 2021. Accelerating the Fourth Industrial Revolution in higher education: Realities and lessons from universities in Kenya, Zambia and South Africa during the Covid-19 pandemic. *European Journal of Economics, Law and Social Sciences*, December: 197–208.
- Maisiri, W., Darwish, H. and van Dyk, L. 2019. An investigation of Industry 4.0 skills requirements. *South African Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 30(3): 90–105.*

- Mamela, T.L., Sukdeo, N. and Mukwakungu, S.C. 2020. Adapting to artificial intelligence through workforce re-skilling within the banking sector in South Africa. *2020 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Computing and Data Communication Systems (icABCD)*, 1–9.
- Mamphiswana, R. and Sinha, S. 2019. Management of technological innovation in emerging economies: A conceptual framework. *Conference Proceedings*.
- Mamushiane, L., Shozi, T. and Manqele, L. 2021. IPv6 adoption in South Africa: Barriers, benefits and government intervention. *IST-Africa 2021 Conference Proceedings*, 1–10.
- Maponya, C.M. and Naidoo, L.D. 2023. Investigating the leaders' state of readiness in the Department of Telecommunications and Postal Services in South Africa to develop policy for the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 23(1): e2833.*
- Marivate, V., Aghoghovwia, P., Ismail, Y., Mahomed-Asmail, F. and Steenhuisen, S-L. 2021. The Fourth Industrial Revolution – what does it mean to our future faculty? *South African Journal of Science*, 117(5/6).
- Masinde, M. and Soux, P. 2020. Transforming South Africa's Universities of Technology: A roadmap through 4IR lenses. *Journal of Construction Project Management and Innovation*, 10(2), 30–50.*
- Mbiza, M. and Sinha, S. 2023. The Fourth Industrial Revolution: Conceptual paradox or catalyst for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals? *South African Journal of Science*, 119(7/8), 1–3.*
- Mhlanga, D. and Moloi, T. 2020. COVID-19 and the digital transformation of education: What are we learning on 4IR in South Africa? *Education Sciences*, 10(7): 180.*
- Moloi, T. and Mhlanga, D. 2021. Key features of the Fourth Industrial Revolution in South Africa's basic education system. *Journal of Management Information and Decision Sciences*, 24(5): 1–20.
- Moloi, T. and Salawu, M. 2024. Institutionalising technologies in South African universities: The imperatives in the Fourth Industrial Revolution era. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Education Research*, 6: 1–19.*
- Mtotywa, M.M., Seabi, M.A., Manqele, T.J., Ngwenya, S.P. and Moetsi, M. 2024. Critical factors for restructuring the education system during the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution in South Africa. *Development Southern Africa*, 41(1): 16–37.*
- Ngoepe, M., Jacobs, L. and Mojapelo, M. 2022. Inclusion of digital records in the archives and records management curricula in a comprehensive open distance e-learning environment. *Information Development*.
- Nhede, N.T., Mazenda, A. and Masiya, T. 2022. The South African public service and the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *Africa's Public Service Delivery & Performance Review*, 10(1): 1–13.
- Nkosi, T.L., Nkomo, M.W. and Ramabodu, S.M. 2023. Fourth Industrial Revolution game changers: The case of South African tertiary institutions. *Proceedings of the 8th North American Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, Houston, USA, June.*

- Nwosu, L.I., Bereng, M.C., Segotso, T. and Enebe, N.B. 2023. Fourth Industrial Revolution tools to enhance the growth and development of teaching and learning in higher education institutions: A systematic literature review in South Africa. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 8(1): 51–62.
- Obioha, C.L. and van Zyl, I. 2022. Gameful design for skills development of youths in marginalised urban communities. *Interaction Design and Architecture(s) Journal*, 53: 27–50.*
- Oke, A. and Fernandes, F.A.P. 2020. Innovations in teaching and learning: Exploring the perceptions of the education sector on the 4th Industrial Revolution. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(2): 31.
- Olaitan, O. and Mavuso, N. 2022. Skilling and reskilling students for relevance in a 4IR economy. *Proceedings of NEMISA Summit and Colloquium*, 88–101.*
- Oliver, W.H. 2020. Teaching theology in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *HTS Teologiese Studies / Theological Studies*, 76(2):a5940.
- Phoobane, P. 2022. Fourth Industrial Revolution research outputs in Africa: A bibliometric review. *International Conference on Emerging Technologies for Developing Countries*, 140–160.
- Pillay, N., Maharaj, B.T. and van Eeden, G. 2018. AI in engineering and computer science education in preparation for the 4th Industrial Revolution: A South African perspective. *2018 World Engineering Education Forum - Global Engineering Deans Council (WEEF-GEDC)*, 1–5.
- Quan, C. 2020. Two passions, one goal, and a pandemic: The future of medical education in South Africa. *Southern African Journal of Anaesthesia and Analgesia*, S11–S13.
- Ramakrishna, S., Ngowi, A., Jager, H.D. and Awuzie, B.O. 2020. Emerging industrial revolution: Symbiosis of Industry 4.0 and circular economy: The role of universities. *Science, Technology and Society*, 25(3): 505–525.
- Saba, C.S. and Ngepah, N. 2024. The impact of artificial intelligence on employment and economic growth in BRICS: Does the moderating role of governance matter? *Research in Globalization*, 8: 100213.
- Safodien, M. 2021. Social Work 4.0? The Fourth Industrial Revolution and social work education: A South African perspective. *Social Work / Maatskaplike Werk*, 57(3): 257–271.*
- Sehlako, N., Chibambo, M.I. and Divala, J.J. 2023. The Fourth Industrial Revolution in South Africa's basic education: A search for cogent curriculum justice. *Frontiers in Education*, 8: 1209511.*
- Serumaga-Zake, J.M. and van der Poll, J.A. 2021. Addressing the impact of Fourth Industrial Revolution on South African manufacturing small and medium enterprises (SMEs). *Sustainability*, 13(21): 11703.
- Sibiya, P.T. 2024. Incorporating digital scholarship content in South African library and information science schools. *Library Management*, 45(3/4): 243–257.
- Singaram, S. and Mayer, C-H. 2022. The influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on organisational culture: An empirical investigation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13: 919157.

- Singaram, S., Mayer, C-H. and Oosthuizen, R.M. 2023. Leading higher education into the Fourth Industrial Revolution: An empirical investigation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14: 1242835.*
- Sukdeo, N.I. and Mothilall, D. 2023. The impact of artificial intelligence on the manufacturing sector: A systematic literature review of the printing and packaging industry. *2023 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Computing and Data Communication Systems (icABCD)*, 1–5.*
- Sutherland, E. 2020. The Fourth Industrial Revolution – the case of South Africa. *Politikon*, 47(2): 233–252.*
- Telukdarie, A. and Munsamy, M. 2019. Digitisation of higher education institutions. *2019 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)*, 716–721.*
- Thani, X.C. 2020. Local economic development (LED) and the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR). *Administratio Publica*, 28(3): 81–97.
- Turpin, M., Mathee, M., Kruger, S. and van Belle, J-P. 2020. Assisting information systems students to engage with the Internet of Things (IoT). *2020 10th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence)*, 552–558.
- van der Poll, J.A. 2022. A research agenda for embedding 4IR technologies in the leadership management of formal methods. *2022 International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence (CSCI)*, 1837–1842.
- van Rensburg, N.J., Telukdarie, A. and Dhamija, P. 2019. Society 4.0 applied in Africa: Advancing the social impact of technology. *Technology in Society*, 59: 101125.
- Vijayalekshmi, S., Twetwa-Dube, S., Vinoth-Kumar, D. and Gumbo, S. 2023. The role of higher education institutions in enabling the Fourth Industrial Revolution: A bibliometric analysis. *2023 IEEE AFRICON*, 1–3.
- Yende, S.J. 2021. A transition towards the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) in the South African education sector: A perspective from rural-based higher education. *African Journal of Development Studies*, 11(2): 55–75.*
- Zulu, S., Pretorius, T. and van der Lingen, E. 2021. The strategic competitiveness of the South African mining industry in the age of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. *The South African Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 32(2): 185–200.
- Zyl, E.V., Venter, T. and Bruwer, J-P. 2021. The catalysed use of Fourth Industrial Revolution interventions in South African higher education institutions due to COVID-19 and its influence on efficacy. *Expert Journal of Business and Management*, 9(1): 64–73.*

* Papers from the Systematic Literature Review included in this references list.

Other References

- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2): 77–101.
- Harwood, T.G. and Garry, T. 2003. An overview of content analysis. *The Marketing Review*, 3(4): 479–498.
- Lewis, M.W. and Smith, W.K. 2014. Paradox as a metatheoretical perspective: Sharpening the focus and widening the scope. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 50(2): 127–149.
- Smith, W.K. and Lewis, M.W. 2011. Toward a theory of paradox: A dynamic equilibrium model of organizing. *Academy of Management Review*, 36(2): 381–403.
- Webster, J., & Watson, R. T. (2002). Analyzing the past to prepare for the future: Writing a literature review. *MIS quarterly*, xiii-xxiii.